

DIGIVET

UK Stakeholder Workshop

Executive Summary

Challenge: Transboundary control and prevention of diseases affecting both animals and humans is at the top of UK animal and public health agendas for government policymakers and has substantial societal impact via both economic drivers and direct impact on human health. Rapid detection and response to relevant threats is only possible if there are effective and resilient surveillance systems with the capacity to detect, assess and disseminate disease intelligence. The exponential growth of data generation to support these systems has vastly outpaced the development of sustainable solutions for data-ecosystem management, verification, and societal access within livestock production and regulatory bodies.

There is an urgent need to collate and characterise the relevant veterinary and animal health data being collected to identify shortcomings and opportunities for improving data accessibility and interoperability, and to contribute software tools and metadata libraries that will facilitate international collaboration, support disease prevention and preparedness, and underpin a wide range of future research in animal and human population health. This report explores:

- What currently works well in the digital data lifecycle to support the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services (for endemic, exotic and foodborne disease preparedness and response)?
- What are the major challenges (gaps and roadblocks) now, and in the next 10 years, for the digitalisation of the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?
- Root causes and solutions for a long-term sustainable solutions to digitalisation of veterinary services.

Key stakeholder messages:

- The approach to building data systems appears to be largely sector-specific, sometimes narrow or isolated in scope, and largely extractive in nature (i.e., without including the data originator in the design innovation process).
- Interoperability with other sectors is often not considered or remains a secondary concern.
- Transmission, sharing and communication of data is typically poor.
- Data collection and use appears to work well only within certain sector-specific lifecycles. For example, animal electronic tagging data which are routinely captured digitally, and in close to real time are a good example of where data collection for animal health is efficient (i.e. few errors, limited interoperability challenges). The otherwise fragmented and diverse nature of data collection leads to silos of data and potentially some oversights with respect to important, but difficult-to-find data.
- Return value (i.e., who the data is for, who benefits and why it benefits them) is not as well prioritised as data collection and use.
- The legislative framework for data access, sharing and use is opaque and there is a fear of non-compliance with GDPR which creates bottlenecks in the system. Negative reinforcement of some aspects of compulsory data collection for government and industry purposes and fears that giving away data may erode trust between farmers and the institutions that are committed to supporting them.

Important areas identified for future investment and exploration:

- Data generation and sharing as part of farmers' business models.
- Public subsidisation to drive data access.
- Investments to address supply chain issues.
- Real-time automated data collection systems wherever possible and demonstration of benefits.
- Agreements on data formats and standards to improve harmonisation.
- Improved governance of data lifecycle- including promotion of data hubs.
- Research-driven roadmaps to address queries and resolve "data ownership and control" problems when they arise for stakeholders and models of data-sharing practices.
- Stakeholder-driven communication networks and improved quality of messaging for better buy-in.
- Education and training initiatives to improve digital literacy and technology uptake.

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Context

Transboundary control and prevention of diseases affecting both animals and humans is at the top of Nordic and UK animal and public health agendas for government policymakers and has substantial societal impact via both economic drivers and direct impact on human health. The ethical responsibility for maintaining human and animal health is fundamentally societal, but specific tasks relating to monitoring, maintaining, and acting on data are disseminated across various government and industry bodies. As a result, related data are gathered and held separately by a variety of entities (both public and private), standards and systems are not consistent across nations, and social and political realities vary substantially by disease and region. However, rapid detection and response to relevant threats is only possible if there are effective and resilient surveillance systems with the capacity to detect, assess and disseminate disease intelligence.

The exponential growth of data generation has vastly outpaced the development of sustainable solutions for data-ecosystem management, verification, and societal access within livestock production and regulatory bodies. As the volume and types of technologies employed to collect those data change and grow, the sustainability of data quality over the long-term becomes unclear; data retention schedules and procedures for disease outbreak data and disease surveillance strategies become less transparent; and the legal, ethical, and social consequences of different roles and responsibilities with the supply chain and for end-users and beneficiaries become more difficult to anticipate.

There is an urgent need to collate and characterise the relevant data being collected across the Nordic countries and the UK in order to identify shortcomings and opportunities for improving data accessibility and interoperability, and to contribute software tools and metadata libraries that will facilitate international collaboration, support disease prevention and preparedness, and underpin a wide range of future research in animal and human population health.

The DigiVet project aims to gather information about how digital data relating to the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services is acquired, managed and used in the UK and Scandinavia to support decision-making about foodborne, animal and zoonotic diseases with potentially high economic impact (such as *Salmonella* infections, African swine fever, antimicrobial resistance (AMR)). The longer-term goal of the DigiVet project is to work with stakeholders to produce a series of prototype decision-support tools for livestock data analysis and visualisation to improve the use and return value of digital data in the sector.

Effective communication and stakeholder engagement is a vital part of the DigiVet project and evidence-informed policy decisions. Knowledge exchange and participatory approaches and activities attached to this project are seen as an equal and integral proactive part of the capacity building role within the scientific process. This workshop intended to operationalize a “data to knowledge” continuum, proactively shaping the pathway from research to impact by taking an inclusive, stakeholder-oriented approach from the outset. ‘Stakeholders’, in this context is used to broadly refer to livestock industry partners, organizational representation from other industries with an interest in animal and public health, university and research institute partners, and individuals at the grass-roots level (industry, regulatory and general public).

Methods and Approach

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework was adapted from Zhang et al. 2022¹ to understand the components of the data lifecycle which are “necessary to produce real world data usable for analysis”². We used this framework as a starting point by which we could identify, compare, and contrast enabling societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) drivers and barriers (as identified by stakeholders) to data digitalisation and innovation of new technologies in veterinary services.

Stakeholders’ perceptions of current challenges, opportunities and knowledge gaps

A participatory workshop was held with key national stakeholders to explore the challenges in data digitalisation and identify key opportunities for developing solutions.

Specifically, we considered:

- What currently works well in the digital data lifecycle to support the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services (for endemic, exotic and foodborne disease preparedness and response)?
- What are the major challenges (gaps and roadblocks) now, and in the next 10 years, for the digitalisation of the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?
- Root causes and solutions for a long-term sustainable solutions to digitalisation of veterinary services.

Our secondary aim was also to investigate attitudes, assumptions and risk perceptions amongst stakeholders, about:

- Current use of digital data in animal health management, for different farm systems.
- Technical, cultural, social or economic enablers or constraints related to acquisition, aggregation, management, application, use and benefits of digital data for livestock health and welfare.
- Other factors affecting digital adoption on farms, markets, abattoirs etc.
- Ethical, legal and regulatory issues which influence public and stakeholder opinion, trust and return value of digital data- including privacy protection and data sharing policies.
- Opportunities to strengthen digitalisation of the livestock sector to improve surveillance and livestock health

The workshop was facilitated by three members of the Skillfluence organisation. DigiVet team members took part in the workshop as participants. Ethical approval for the workshop was obtained from the University of Edinburgh research ethics committee.

Participants and the project team were tasked with engaging in strategic thinking through a series of carefully crafted exercises (in three small groups and plenary) to explore:

¹ Zhang J, Symons J, Agapow P, Teo JT, Paxton CA, Abdi J, et al. (2022) Best practices in the real-world data life cycle. PLOS Digit Health 1(1): e0000003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000003>

² *Ibid*

- What is working well
- Challenges (i.e., gaps, roadblocks, opportunities and uncertainties)
- Prioritising critical challenges
- Identifying route causes
- Proposing solutions.

Participants recorded their ideas on an online whiteboard (Miro). Scribes in each of the small groups transcribed paraphrased notes on paper. The session was also recorded on zoom with permission of participants for the purposes of supporting the information gathering in each session. The workshop was held under Chatham House Rule – meaning that contributions were anonymised and aggregated, and not attributed to individuals nor their organisations.

Results

Stakeholder Demographics

Participant stakeholders were invited to attend a half-day event, held online through a secure Zoom platform. Stakeholders comprised a multidisciplinary audience (~34 people, >50% female) from diverse backgrounds including the following sectors: farming, livestock (pigs), policy, industry, governance (at devolved, national and intergovernmental levels) and research (reflecting social science, veterinary medicine, epidemiology, law and policy). Participants from the private sector (i.e. online data platforms for livestock data) were invited but did not attend.

Stakeholder Expectations

Stakeholders were provided with information about the project and the workshop aims ahead of the event and were invited to reflect on their expectations. The following observations may articulate participant expectations about the event but may also provide some insight into the challenges faced by stakeholders with respect to digitalisation of veterinary services to better prepare and respond to risks to animal health and welfare.

- Dialogue around upstream drivers of data digitalisation
- Identify other data sources which could be useful
- Simplifying data access and sharing, particularly from industry and for research purposes
- Better understanding of barriers to data use, and pragmatic approaches to overcoming these.
- Understanding how others are dealing with certain issues – such as privacy agreements etc.
- Interested in how data ecosystems differ depending on different species and disease concerns
- A better sense of the wider digital picture.
- Keep up to date with current thinking
- Focus on knowledge and skills of people
- Trust and technology
- Supporting new and better strategies for the future

What is Working Well

A description of what is “working well” is presented in Table 1. Stakeholder consensus was that data production and to some degree, acquisition is an area where the data lifecycle is working “well” but not perhaps optimally.

Key Messages

- Animal data which are routinely captured digitally, and in close to real time (i.e., animal movement data) was highlighted as a good example of where data collection for animal health is efficient. The data are considered to be generally clean (i.e., few errors), with limited interoperability challenges (such as linking datasets). Electronic tagging plays an important role in this.
- Transmission, sharing and communication of data is typically poor. There are silos of “good data” which are generated, but then inaccessible or “lost” to the system.
- Data collection and use appears to work well within certain sector-specific lifecycles.
- Return value (i.e., who the data is for, who benefits and why it benefits them) is not as well prioritised as data collection and use.

What are the Major Challenges?

Participants identified a number of major challenges: gaps, roadblocks, uncertainties – and also opportunities (see Tables 2A-D for a detailed summary for each group). Most of the gaps and roadblocks identified were associated with data production and acquisition, whereas the uncertainties amongst stakeholders seemed to be located around the return value of the data system and the attitudes, beliefs or assumptions held by the data beneficiaries (who may also be the data originators). Participants focussed primarily on farmers, and veterinarians as the people who should collect and share data, whereas other actors such as retailers, processors, or government groups who could or should share data, were not prioritised as highly.

Key Messages

- There is a diversity of methods of data collection and different roles and responsibilities associated with this, which leads to some confusion about who is producing what, when and for whom. The fragmented nature of this approach leads to silos of data and potentially some oversights with respect to important, but difficult-to-find data (e.g., on wildlife reservoirs).
- Farmer uptake of technology for data reporting is mixed. Data are often collected for different purposes than health and this is perceived to have an impact on the willingness to participate and share information.
- The legislative framework for data access, sharing and use is opaque and there is a fear of non-compliance with GDPR which creates bottlenecks in the system (i.e., data sharing agreements).
- Farmers don't appear to benefit directly from data-sharing (i.e., this is not monetised in the same way that it might be for supermarkets; feedback loops are not well-evidenced; absence of meaningful incentives). Benefits of data collection for surveillance (i.e., health) may not be well-aligned with the perceived farmer benefits (i.e. profit motives). However, this was an area of uncertainty for participants, who felt that more needed to be done to explore these assumptions.

Table 1. Summary: What currently works well in the digital data lifecycle to support the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?

Breakout group	Data Acquisition (connectivity, wearables, electronic identification, decision-support tools, diagnostics etc.)	Data Aggregation and Processing (data handling, interoperability, harmonisation etc.)	Data Management and Maintenance (partitioning, access, security etc.)	Data Usage (retrieval, analytics, insights for policy, decision-making, ethics etc)	Return Value (Costs, relevance, user-friendliness, trust, transparency etc)
1.	<p>Industry-led initiatives to capture production data AMU– especially for pig and poultry sectors where data may be already digitalised. APHA diagnostic data and VIDA codes (assuming a diagnosis). Traceability data for livestock seems generally good , easy for farmers to input into and reasonably well-integrated (but not necessarily across borders).</p>	<p>Not reported.</p>	<p>Generation and local storage of data seems easy for some sectors.</p>	<p>Data that is accessible is used to inform policy decisions. Data sharing for outbreaks. When accessible, use of data by boundary organisations such as EPIC is efficient.</p>	<p>Data for outbreak preparedness seems to work reasonably well. Systems designed for specific use cases.</p>
2.	<p>Surveillance data for antibiotic sales. Electronic tagging. Statutory requirements for reporting data on livestock diseases (such as BVD), mortality (i.e. births and deaths) and for traceability purposes (i.e. movement data). Ease of reporting through new technologies: touch screens in slaughterhouses. Dairy herd improvement programs, such as using milk quality data for making production management decisions. Data collected in abattoirs on carcass quality, lesions, and partial condemnations used to optimize production in swine production systems Health schemes. Iterative improvements to tech, e.g. updating scales used to weigh lambs (allowing for easier & more reliable data collection; more data over a longer period can show patterns).</p>	<p>Not reported.</p>	<p>ScotEID website (Scotland) with multiple levels of access to permit appropriate data sharing within the livestock sector.</p>	<p>Identifying new threats – horizon scanning, data mining efforts. (From discussion) Use of regulatory frameworks that take into account differences in settings, e.g. SMART regulation for antibiotics</p>	<p>Agreement by many actors that animal health data should be used for the public good. Data dashboards available to the public (see APHA Gateway - (APHA Vet Gateway: Livestock disease surveillance dashboards (defra.gov.uk)).</p>
3.	<p>Cattle tracing system generally offers clean data. Recording and storage of demographic, management and production data as well as of other health and management associated-information. Generally good (formal and informal communication structures) between stakeholders. eMB improving accuracy of data capture of medicine use year on year. Pig movement licences are all created before departure. Collaboration between private vets and sharing data. Movement data works well and the system is largely trusted by farmers.</p>	<p>Good and accurate linking of data across systems suggests errors are minimal. There is an established coding system for veterinary diagnoses that is standard and yields records of animal disease occurrence. Reasonably well harmonised across the UK VIDA data provides consistency across UK surveillance.</p>		<p>Once data agreements are in place, academic use of data works well. Reasonable flexibility to pro-actively investigate outbreaks.</p>	<p>Clear guidance in place for farmers to improve disease detection.</p>

Table 2A Knowledge gaps in the digitalisation of the livestock sector and related veterinary services

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
1.	<p>Missing baseline data.</p> <p>Lack of 'go to' system for farmers- lots of competitive system.</p> <p>Farmer uptake - not just a technological solution - examples where good apps exist but aren't used.</p> <p>Lack of access to data. i.e. slaughter details for producer who sells through a market.</p> <p>Missing data for certain sectors – perhaps where regulatory frameworks are missing – e.g. exact numbers of feral pigs in Scotland (which are an ASF risk) are unknown.</p> <p>who are the data "owners" and what considerations need to be given to this.</p> <p>No way of recording "unknown unknowns" i.e. potential emerging diseases.</p> <p>Data is collected for different purpose than we want to use it for.</p>	<p>AMR results from private veterinary labs – in silos; absence of standardisation.</p>	<p>Not reported.</p>	<p>Lack of existing elements in data models to support future integration.</p> <p>Complex data sharing agreements.</p>	<p>Enough evidence for future value to support current buy-in to integration.</p> <p>Feedback loops back to the data producer (I.e., the farmer).</p>
2.	<p>Farmers are not engaged with getting disease information, so the data is not generated in the first place.</p> <p>Lack of engagement of data providers and information users in the data life cycle. This is especially the case for farmers who provide much of the data we need for surveillance, but perceive that they do not receive anything in return.</p> <p>No consistency between how data is collected, each abattoir has its own system. Not all abattoirs have a digital recording system. There is no centralised data platform for all abattoirs in Scotland.</p> <p>In UK large amounts of data is in private practices/labs and is not accessible for country wide surveillance.</p> <p>There are gaps in farm level identifiers in some of the datasets, eg diagnostic laboratory data. Where there are farm level identifiers, they are often considered to be personal data and data collectors are reluctant to share because of the GDPR and their desire to maintain the trust of their clients.</p>	<p>Data is in lots of different places so there is limited view of the bigger picture.</p>	<p>Data is in lots of different places so there is limited view of the bigger picture.</p> <p>Mandatory data sharing works well (e.g. Salmonella, zoonotic disease exemplars). In an endemic disease context, data sharing works within projects on a small scale, but it is challenging to bring it together, in the absence of centralised funding for infrastructure and resources.</p>	<p>Accessing private lab data is a gap/ obstacle for surveillance</p> <p>Use of private labs may lead to dispersion of data.</p>	<p>No common vision yet for how health and welfare data should be used between industry/ government/other stakeholders. The interest in animal health and welfare between stakeholders is different.</p>
3.	<p>Too many different ways of data collection - a one stop shop would be helpful.</p> <p>Who takes ownership of data?</p> <p>We don't know who has what data even if it is captured- vets/farmers etc. having data and then not knowing where to submit it.</p> <p>Pig movements a little less well-established than cattle.</p> <p>AMU/AMR data in general.</p> <p>.</p>	<p>Very rarely different data streams (e.g. animal/on farm and genomic data) are integrated and analysed in a combined way.</p> <p>Link between production data and other streams - could be much richer in value if data could be integrated.</p> <p>No consistent definitions - e.g., when does a heifer become a cow?</p> <p>The notion that biological processes can be rendered into records in a database.</p>	<p>Difficult to know who has the data you need and what you would need to do to access it.</p>		

Table 2B Existing and anticipated roadblocks in the next 10 years for digitalisation of the livestock sector and related veterinary services

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
1.	<p>Age demographics of farming population.</p> <p>Fear of transparency</p> <p>Lack of trust.</p> <p>Reluctance to give data to government (dependent on sector).</p> <p>Lack of clarity about data ownership.</p> <p>Buy-in to certain issues (e.g. AMR).</p> <p>Lack of a clear regulatory framework for certain uses of technology.</p> <p>Mistrust over secondary uses of data.</p> <p>Data recording system design- and lack of future-proofed and coherent visions.</p> <p>GDPR – queries over the status of CPH [council parish holding number].</p> <p>Commercial sensitivity of the data and its potential loss.</p> <p>Private small businesses are the ones generating data.</p>	<p>Many different systems.</p> <p>Data silos.</p> <p>Disaggregation of GB wide systems.</p> <p>Difficulties orchestrating different data sources due to different formats in which data is collected, different terminologies used etc.</p>	<p>Data Sharing agreements slow.</p>	<p>Disease outbreaks (i.e. avian influenza) meaning industry resources are stretched, and so data sharing takes longer.</p> <p>Problems with data retrieval.</p>	<p>Legal and privacy constraints/lack of perceived value to overcome these failure to give back value to farmers for use of their data.</p>
2.	<p>Data ownership.</p> <p>Farmer data collection and auditing fatigue.</p>	<p>Lack of tech/resource for data cleaning/mining to share.</p> <p>Gaps in expertise.</p>	<p>Setting up data sharing agreements.</p> <p>Do not have the software/hardware/resource or expertise to manage/ share data from vets.</p> <p>Lack of sufficient incentives for data sharing, lack of trust (that data are anonymised, and not used to penalise the provider, industry or way of life).</p> <p>Vets are reluctant to share data with government due to confidentiality and freedom of information requests sharing of some public health data such as AMR is voluntary.</p> <p>Harmonisation of data collection/units i.e. what we should collect; how should it be collected.</p>	<p>Gaps in expertise on data protection law amongst those who are seeking to collect, use, share data. Delays result from consulting remote legal authorities.</p>	<p>Gaps in expertise.</p>

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
			<p>Work is required on minimum datasets to describe epidemiological events, for various purposes.</p> <p>Newer approaches include: output-based surveillance (i.e., standardising the outputs rather than data themselves).</p> <p>There are still gaps in data standards and in methods standardising the confidence with which one can make these statements, as opposed to regulation-based standards of type "test x percentage of animals with method y".</p> <p>Infrastructure: speed of the line, layout, old design of the buildings and no room for too many improvements.</p>		
3.	<p>Difficulty and time gathering/submitting data on farm if the process to do so is not automated or part of a scheme like red tractor etc.</p> <p>Often reliant on IT which for many can be a challenge</p> <p>Internet connection for example.</p> <p>Data is collected often for specific purposes and trying to interpret it for something else is a challenge.</p> <p>Slow engagement process with ruminant sector on AMU.</p> <p>Privacy: people don't want to appear in databases.</p> <p>(Cybersecurity)</p> <p>need to understand purpose of data, so can ensure its collected and managed in the right way,</p> <p>Data-sharing legislation is constraining,</p>	<p>Reliability of data - especially that gathered 'in the field'.</p>	<p>Data sharing agreements are slow.</p>	<p>Epidemiology has its limitations: it doesn't work well for individuals.</p> <p>Multidisciplinary collaboration difficult.</p>	<p>Lack of incentives.</p> <p>Sometimes data needed by one part of the supply chain needs to be supplied by another - how to incentivise?</p> <p>Evidence importance/utility of data to stakeholders.</p> <p>Money: specifically for resolution of data and IT investment at abattoir.</p>

Table 2C Opportunities in the next 10 years for digitalisation of the livestock sector and related veterinary services.

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
1.	<p>On line medicine records, mortality and production records etc. Providing access to other bodies reducing inspections. Requiring agreement to data share if in receipt of public monies. Update data recording systems for more effective data capture. More farm-level data. Vets are often very motivated to share for surveillance purposes.</p>	<p>Easy interrogation of One Health data across different sectors (animal, human, food, environment). Integration of other sources of data related to public interests (i.e. maximise co-benefits of data collection and sharing through different systems)</p>	<p>Improvements in data sharing within and between government organisations and sectors.</p>	<p>Data for benchmarking. Real-time data analysis.</p>	<p>Farmers will compare notes if useful to them/doesn't feel like invasion of privacy. Subsidy as an incentive for data provision. More funding for research into how to achieve joined up approaches to good practices across the data cycle. Educating industry colleagues as to why data sharing benefits them (as well as government and wider industry). Better ways of communicating information in privacy policies.</p>
2.	<p>Development of user-friendly platforms e.g., apps for easy, portable digital data recording that can be uploaded to a dashboard/database. Vet e-prescriptions or barcoded medicine doses to better monitor AMU rather than just antibiotic sales. Apps or systems for vets/farmers to log disease information.</p>	<p>Taking a One Health approach and uniting human and non-human health concerns and data under one regulatory framework (e.g., zero Rabies). Linking animal health records with animal movement records. Have a consistent approach across sectors/organisations/places for data collection (e.g., abattoirs). Privatisation of data to protect farmers/businesses. Anonymisation of data; creation of synthetic data that is statistically identical to real data but not traceable - e.g., DataSHIELD (https://www.datashield.org/). But requires trust into such products/companies, + costs may be an issue. There is a perception that, in Europe, governments are taking on more responsibility in animal health in recent years, possibly driven by climate change. Many recent EU programmes to help livestock industry respond to rapidly changing conditions, requiring different disciplines working together. This comes with a shift in focus towards "health" rather than individual diseases.</p>	<p>Better IT infrastructure for transfer and storage of data.</p>	<p>Unified coding systems such as VeNom for easier analysis. There is a need to train more analysts with livestock and veterinary public health domain expertise.</p>	<p>Not reported.</p>
3.	<p>Ground-truthing: Recognise that there is a need to talk</p>	<p>Consistent identification of premises, holdings, flocks, herds, etc.</p>			<p>Feedback to those providing the data (farmers, Private Veterinary Services, etc).</p>

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
	<p>to real people rather than just work with arrays of records. A one stop shop for example medicine recording. Not everything can be boiled down to numbers - some things rely on observations, people knowing their animals etc. Most animal ID isn't electronic so there's a clumsy step right at the beginning joining ID to other data. Integration of clinical data (disease syndromes and clinical diseases) – VeNOM Capitalise on secondary data use could allow for new opportunities to more holistically monitor animal health and production (including animal movements, environmental and weather data, etc).</p>	<p>Building data systems that are fit for purpose. Make platforms speak to each other better. Standardisation of clinical information recording (and for that matter any other entries in data - geographic, herd IDs, etc). Common data standards.</p>			<p>Incentives to improve digital literacy and “laggards’ with respect to technology adoptions. Demonstrate value in data/intelligence to those who provide it.</p>

Table 2D Stakeholder uncertainties about digitalisation of the livestock sector and related veterinary services.

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
1.	<p>Do we know the questions we want to ask? Are the data correct (accurate, robust).</p>		<p>Detailed reasons why data sharing between industry and government is so difficult/takes so long.</p>	<p>Political support for disease surveillance (investment in preparedness). Govt IT procurement processes.</p>	<p>Farmer and veterinarian motivations for not participating in data collection. Stakeholder perceptions about risks and trust (i.e., is it mistrust or just a lack of time). What is it about the systems that work well and are trusted that makes them work and trusted?</p>
2.	<p>Who owns data- usually designated to the party that adds the most value to the data? Or perhaps those that collect the data? Can data from industry be protected from freedom of information requests? = Sustaining resourcing of proactive rather than reactive surveillance is challenging. Institutional memory loss means that funding may be diverted in the absence of any outbreaks (i.e., when surveillance enables successful mitigation of outbreaks).</p>			<p>Covid has shown the value of including non-human health / anticipatory animal logic but how to implement these concerns for future pandemic preparedness. For endemic disease, there is a need for some form of centralised regulation, but whose remit should this be (government or industry bodies)? E.g., control of sheep scab was regulated by gov, then deregulated & left to be managed by industry, after which it skyrocketed. Political differences in countries within the UK, may result in different willingness of government to step in and regulate. E.g., in Scotland & NI, government stepped in to regulate BVD regulation -but not in England & Wales.</p>	<p>Whether industry understands the need to encourage data sharing. Who benefits from data collection and use: Animals/farmers/consumers/government industry? Stakeholder perceptions of risk. Can we actually get everybody on the same page (meat industry).</p>
3.	<p>GB/UK and variations in different regions - disease doesn't recognise borders but politics is making complications. Who is in charge of the data collection process?</p>	<p>Interoperable data management systems.</p>	<p>How to improve data sharing, while protecting privacy and security.</p>	<p>Best ways of producing analytic tools or insights that are of use to industry.</p>	<p>The long-term viability of the internet. Information overload. Political direction (e.g. ,Scottish independence with EU regs, etc).</p>

Critical Challenges: High Priority Problems

Groups identified a number of high priority challenges (described in Table 3).

Key Messages

- The approach to building data systems appears to be largely sector-specific, sometimes narrow or isolated in scope, and largely extractive in nature (i.e., without including the data originator in the design innovation process).
- Interoperability with other sectors e.g., human health is often not considered or a secondary concern (e.g., ontology, terminology and reference units may not be consistent).
- Resource-poor farmers and veterinarians may not adopt new technologies or immediately see the value of promised benefits.
- Negative reinforcement of some aspects of compulsory data collection for government and industry purposes (i.e., to meet legal requirements/cross-compliance requirements to receive subsidies) and fears that giving away data may have unintended negative consequences. Over time, this may have eroded trust between farmers and the institutions that are committed to supporting them.

Table 3. Summary of High Priority Challenges Breakout group	Area of Data Lifecycle Impacted
1. Buy-in Agency Ethical-Legal Frameworks	Data Acquisition and Return Value.
2. Investment in surveillance and cooperation (Buy-in) Inaccuracy of data. Ethical-Legal Frameworks (data “ownership”). Harmonisation, interoperability and centralisation. Lack of trust and engagement about data usage.	Data Acquisition and Return Value. Data Aggregation.
3. Time poverty for data originators/creators. Lack of joined up data sharing across organisations. Value of “big data” is not always perceived by those who are relied upon to collect it and share it.	Data Acquisition and Return Value. Data Management.

Root Causes

Participants were asked to explore some of the root causes of these challenges. Each group looked at different challenges. In this section, we have summarised responses where there is significant overlap. For example, each group identified the aspects surrounding engagement with data originators/beneficiaries (i.e., lack of buy-in, lack of trust and engagement, invisibility of the return value of big-data). These were aggregated into Figure 1. Root causes of the challenge associated with “Lack of adequate buy-in to digitalisation of livestock data and veterinary services”. Similarly, aspects of power and agency are associated with the ethico-legal frameworks and are reflected in Figure 2 which describes the root causes of the challenge associated with ethico-legal frameworks not being fit-for-purpose. Figure 3 – which describes root causes associated with lack of harmonisation, standardisation and interoperability reflects the feedback from groups 2 and 3.

The figures also include enumerated critical control points (CCPs) in each system (which were applied to the problem trees post-hoc), but which corresponded to solutions/strategies identified by participants in the next stage of the workshop.

CHALLENGE: Lack of adequate buy-in to digitalization of livestock data and veterinary services

ROOT CAUSE

CHALLENGE: Ethico-legal frameworks for data production, use and benefit are not fit-for-purpose

ROOT CAUSE

CHALLENGE: Insufficient harmonization, standardization and interoperability of data/platforms

Finding Solutions

Participants identified a number of potential solutions or strategies which can be applied at each stage of the data life cycle. These are listed in detail in Table 4 and are linked to the critical control points labelled in Figures 1-3. The idea of a critical control point is borrowed from food safety processes and risk analyses frameworks and is applied in this context to identify places in the problem tree pathways, where mitigation steps could be applied successfully to address the ultimate challenge. In summary these included:

1. Data generation and sharing as part of farmers' business models.
2. Public subsidisation to drive data access.
3. Investments to address supply chain issues.
4. Demonstration of benefits of data collection.
5. Real-time automated data collection systems wherever possible.
6. Agreements on data formats and standards to improve harmonisation.
7. Improved governance of data lifecycle- including promotion of data hubs.
8. Research-driven roadmaps to address queries and resolve "data ownership and control" problems when they arise for stakeholders and models of data-sharing practices.
9. Stakeholder-driven communication networks and improved quality of messaging for better buy-in.
10. Education and training initiatives to improve digital literacy and technology uptake.

Table 4. Stakeholder-led solutions. Reference to critical control points (CCPs) in Figures 1-3 are mapped to each solution.

Breakout group	Data Acquisition	Data Aggregation and Processing	Data Management and Maintenance	Data Usage	Return Value
1.	<p>CCP1. Collect data as part of the farmer business model. Compulsory use of online data recording systems for legally required data (ie funded by public monies). Data regarding specific food animals should be visible from farm to fork (birth, death, medicines, usage, location). This could require electronic identification in species which don't already do this.</p> <p>CCP2. Public subsidies to drive data access.</p> <p>CCP3. Interventions to address supply chain issues: decouple farmers from supermarket incentives to shift agency (see also data usage and return values).</p> <p>CCP4. Shared understanding of the challenges (e.g. AMR) and need for One Health approaches.</p> <p>CCP5. Real-time automated data collection systems (QRS codes with life-history of animal embedded).</p>	<p>CCP6. Enforce common metadata standards.</p>	<p>CCP8. Roadmap for resolving 'data ownership and control' issues.</p> <p>CCP8. Models of data sharing model data-sharing agreements. MTAs to formalise data sharing with farmers.</p>	<p>CCP3. Interventions to address supply chain issues</p> <p>CCP9. Communication network across public and private sectors to specify data needs.</p> <p>Interactive, user-friendly dashboards to visualise data (all-in-one-place).</p>	<p>CCP1. Ensure systems do generate value for farmers and vets. This presupposes monitoring and evaluation processes built into any system.</p> <p>CCP3. Interventions to address supply chain issues</p> <p>CCP10. Educate data consumers</p> <p>Investment in research.</p> <p>CCP1. Prioritise interventions which maximise farm profitability.</p> <p>Marketing campaigns to demonstrate data use.</p>
2.		<p>CCP6. Standardised ontologies and vocabulary.</p>		<p>CCP9. Transparency</p>	<p>CCP9. Improve communication networks- face to face and online to promote transparency over secrecy. These networks should be transdisciplinary.</p> <p>CCP10. Data training.</p> <p>CCP7. Global solidarity across industry leaders in this space.</p>
3.	<p>CCP1. Resource people and data quality – not IT.</p>	<p>CCP6. Agreements on data formats and standards.</p> <p>CCP7. Co-ownership and improved governance of data lifecycle – including data hubs</p>			<p>CCP9. Improved communication networks and quality of messaging for better buy-in- including Proof of principle demonstrations to data originators to improve buy-in.</p> <p>CCP6. Co-ownership with stakeholders.</p>

Discussion

This project has undertaken a participatory approach to gather information about how digital data relating to the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services is acquired, managed and used to support decision-making about foodborne, animal and zoonotic diseases in the UK. The aim is to ultimately co-design with stakeholders, a series of prototype decision-support tools for livestock data analysis and visualisation to improve the use and return value of digital data in the sector.

Participants identified a number of important challenges for digitalisation of veterinary services. Although technological innovation is clearly a key area for future development to improve data collection and sharing, the greatest source of uncertainty amongst stakeholders was about the social benefit of any digitalised veterinary system i.e., the return value of the data system for data beneficiaries such as farmers, and veterinarians.

This predominant focus on technological opportunities and challenges was likely due to:

- The expertise and experience of participants in attendance i.e., few farmer representatives to push back on the idea that data acquisition is primarily the responsibility of farmers;
- A perceived lack of agreement about how data should be used for what purposes; Fluency and familiarity with technical language and problem solving as opposed to other concepts (e.g., political, legal, ethical).

Farmer uptake of technology was considered to be highly variable and it was not evident how farmers currently benefit economically from data-sharing. Furthermore, the benefits of data collection for surveillance (i.e. health) may not be well-aligned with the perceived farmer benefits (i.e. profit motives). An interesting theme that emerged in discussion, was that farmers may be very interested in accessing other farmer data, but not necessarily willing to open their own data for wider sharing. The latter raises many interesting practical, ethical, game theoretical and sociological issues for further exploration.

A number of Critical Control Points (CCPs) were identified by participants to optimise solution-building efforts. Many of these were focused (directly or indirectly) on the issue of farmer- and veterinarian-derived benefit, namely:

- CCP 1. Data generation and sharing as part of farmers' business models.
- CCP 3. Investments to address supply chain issues.
- CCP 4. Demonstration of benefits of data collection.
- CCP 8. Research-driven roadmaps to address queries and resolve "data ownership and control" problems when they arise for stakeholders and models of data-sharing practices.
- CCP 9. Stakeholder-driven communication networks and improved quality of messaging for better buy-in.
- CCP 10. Education and training initiatives to improve digital literacy and technology uptake.

The data landscape is complex and ownership of digitalisation strategies seemed unclear to participants. Trusted data brokers are likely to become increasingly important if there is a desire to impose data and meta-data standards and other technological prerequisites for digitalisation which are so far missing from existing services, but nonetheless identified as important and desirable by participants.

Next steps

The DigiVet project runs from 2020-2023. The results of this workshop were used to inform the design of a pig movement data digitalisation tool relevant to the control of African swine fever. The next step in the project is the organisation of three international workshops involving stakeholders from the UK, Sweden, Denmark, Norway and Estonia. These workshops will explore the use of data digitalisation tools developed in the project in relation to African swine fever (UK workshop), Salmonella CS (Denmark) and antibiotic use (Sweden). The workshops will take a holistic approach considering the practicality and efficacy of the tools in addressing technological roadblocks and wider governance and ethical issues related to data digitalisation.